

Absorption and Extra-sensitisation of some Dimethylamino-benzylidenethionaphthenes

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Recently Guha *et al.*¹ reported the preparation and absorption of the four isomeric 4'-dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(4-, 5-, 6-, and 7-methoxy)thionaphthenes. Now the UV absorption of various methyl- and halogen-substituted 4'-dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-thionaphthenes, previously prepared by Guha *et al.*²⁻³, and of another newly prepared dye, 4'-dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(5, 6-benzo)thionaphthene (I), have been examined and recorded in Table I.

It is interesting to observe that whereas the methyl-substituted dyes have the sequence: 5-Me > 4-Me > 7-Me > 6-Me with regard to their absorption maxima, the methoxy dyes have a slightly different order: 5-OMe > 7-OMe > 4-OMe > 6-OMe. In both the series, the 5-substitution leads to the greatest bathochromic effect, but the 6-substituted dyes have the absorption maxima at the shortest wave length. It will be also seen that among the 5- and 7-substituted compounds, discussed here, the 5-Br and 7-Cl product, respectively, possess the deepest colour.

TABLE I

Compounds.	λ_{max} .	Extra-sensitisation.		Remarks.
		Range.	Maximum.	
D-2-(4-Me)-T	481 m μ	520-590 m μ	530 m μ	Fairly good
D-2-(5-Me)-T	482	520-580	550	Weak
D-2-(6-Me)-T	475	520-620	..	Good; uniform in the whole region.
D-2-(7-Me)-T	479	Nil	..	..
D-2-(4-OMe)-T	471	Nil	..	..
D-2-(5-OMe)-T	491	Almost nil	..	Very feeble
D-2-(6-OMe)-T	460	520-550	520	Feeble
D-2-(7-OMe)-T	482	Nil	..	..
D-2-(7-chloro)-T	490	520-570	..	Very feeble
D-2-(5-bromo)-T	494	520-580	540	Weak
D-2-(5,6-benzo)-T	505	Almost nil	..	Very feeble

N.B.—'D' denotes 4'-dimethylaminobenzylidene, and 'T', thionaphthene.

1. *Chem. Ber.*, 1961, 94, 3297.

2. *This Journal*, 1925, 12, 860; 1937, 14, 709; 1938, 15, 369; 1944, 21, 391; 1951, 29, 103.

3. *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, 92, 2769.

The findings of Brooker⁴ and Kendall⁵ regarding the definite but feeble sensitising property of 4'-dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-thionaphthene and the observation of Sinha⁶ regarding the analogous property of its 6-iodo derivative prompted the present authors to study the photosensitising properties of eleven compounds under report with a view to examining if any relationship could be traced between absorption and photosensitisation of these dyes. The expectation is, however, far from realised as the sensitisation data in Table I show.

The extra-sensitisation of the isomeric methyl compounds can be now arranged in the order: 6-Me > 4-Me > 5-Me > 7-Me. This is entirely different from the order of their colour change stated above. In the methoxy series, only the 6-methoxy compound, although feeble, recorded extra-sensitisation; the remaining three isomeric 4-, 5-, and 7-methoxy compounds exhibited no such property. Of the two halogen compounds, the bromo compound possessed greater extra-sensitising property than the chloro product. The 5,6-benzo compound also revealed no extra-sensitisation.

4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(5,6-benzo)thionaphthene (I).—A solution of 2,3-naphthoxythionaphthene (0.54 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.403 g.) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was boiled for 15 min. with the addition of HCl (conc., 4 ml) and then kept in a cooled chamber for 48 hr. when a brownish yellow crystalline precipitate separated. On washing with hot water the precipitate turned deep red. The compound after boiling with a little dilute NaOH solution for 2-3 min. was crystallised from pyridine and finally dried at 120°; m.p. 239-40° (decomp.). It is soluble in nitrobenzene, pyridine, and glacial acetic acid; moderately soluble in benzene, xylene, and ethanol. It forms a green solution in H₂SO₄ (conc). (Found: N, 4.31. C₂₁H₁₇ONS requires N, 4.22%).

For recording sensitisation, the dye solution, 1/500,000 in 30% rectified spirit, was used and uniformly exposed for 4 min.

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4. B.F. 428,716; 428, 222; 428, 359.

5. U.S.P. 2078, 233; 2069,729.

6. This Journal, 1962, 39, 165.